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THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to reveal aspects of tourism development in Uzbekistan. The Republic of Uzbekistan opening new opportunities to increase International Inbound and Local tourism and this strategy has been proved by the cultural heritage of historical objects also the wonderful types of cuisines providing with hot hospitality of Uzbekistan invite attractions tourists. This study also aims at the international tourism development in Uzbekistan. Foreign tourists come to Uzbekistan with certain motivations and information about Uzbekistan. The basis of this study is to analyse tourist perceptions according the innovative modern trends for Inbound Tourism and preferences of measurement. International Tourism sector should be studied by the correlation analysis to increase the effectiveness of Tourism Development. The main target is to identify of tourists expectations and real travel conditions were studied in tourism field.

Keywords: Empirical analysis, Inbound International Tourism, Opportunities, Tourism Opportunities, hospitality.

Introduction

Uzbekistan work on the Development and modernization of the tourism industry for the sustainable development of the industry. Uzbekistan improves and develops regulatory framework as well as tourist services with International Standards. In developing Tourism Government aimed to put Policies. So, in the future, these should become the main areas for the Integrated development of the country as well as its infrastructure facilities. Development in Tourism creates factors they are new jobs, diversification increasing incomes of regions, increasing quality of life, increasing in the foreign exchange earnings, as well as attractiveness in investment of the country. In 2016-2017 the annual growth rate of tourists was increased from 8% to 33.7%. In 2018 the figure exceeded by

almost 2 times. In 2019 foreign visitors came to Uzbekistan figure was 6,748.500. Questioning was done and studied from the foreign tourist about their expectation and preferences. In Global economy tourism is found of the leading sector that's why in The Tourism Industry the places of Uzbekistan particularly give important for their modern culture. The improvement as well as development of the conceptual framework for the tourism sustainable development as well as international standards in tourist service. Various actions were implemented in Uzbekistan for enhancement and preservation for the cultural heritage of the people as well as custom and traditions attractions and restoration. After the Independence of Uzbekistan cooperation and relationship with International Organization has been increasing actively. As well as their intention always come up with an initiative to make cooperation in Tourism field.

The core of this research is to study modern innovation trends of International Tourism and should be mention the necessary requirements effectively increasing development of tourism in a system analysis by correctly measurements and correlation analysis. The basic of the study is on the trend currently confirms for the Inbound tourism. That's dynamics of Tourism Development and system to identify the tourist expectations and preferences measures to be taken Modernization prospects and realities should be taken in account as well as necessity of specification of tourism filed.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1

According the Figure 1: Conceptual framework, The Tourism Industry is strongly related with Geography and Economic socio-cultural environment

which has relationships between Government and Tourism Development Strategy. At this point of view the strategy of Tourism Development has main sectors in the Transportation field as Railway, Airport and Airline services which generate providing Destination Tourism products in the well-known cities as Bukhara, Samarkand and Khiva Old city. As well as dividing according to tourist purposes as medical, Business (MICE – Meeting, Incentives, Conferences, Exhibitions) or recreation activities.

Literature review

The necessity of a Tourism Development Study increases the demand for Research in the Tourism field. This manuscript reviews the scientific papers by (Kerdpitak, 2022) the study emphasised on the marketing effectiveness model of tourism business in Thailand. The study works on scientific paper which examine about the prospectives in tourism via advanced marketing strategies and their installation for implementation. Generally, studied shows about the tourism involvement settings and emotions according to foreign visitors' conditions and represented their emotions of tourist satisfaction (Santos et al., 2021). Past research of tourism suggested to examine the role of satisfaction in tourist as well as the moderating and mediating roles of playfulness and perceived in the relationship between interpretation of tour guide and loyalty for tourist regarding destination in Taiwan (Cheng et al., 2013); (Chang, 2014); (Chang et al., 2016). In addition to increasing in the knowledge of tourist sustainability by recognizing how people make their mindsets among community stakeholders. This also shows, about theories of negotiated relationship in between regimes of tourism as well as development in an advanced capitalist system (Lindberg et al., 2019). Particularly, Casual Relationships among Tourism International Trade, Pollution, and Economic growth become evidence from Central Asian which based on holding issues in Tourism. The study also emphasized about the sectors among Central Asian countries in the development strategies of tourism (Abdukhamidov et. Al., 2022). (Xudoyarov, 2019) the study emphasized on the role of visiting tourism in the peculiarities and aspects of the tourism industry in the Global markets. The papers suggested that international Tourism is a fast-growing Industry as well as the part of Global economy. Uzbekistan Tourism sector is also switching to represent our country and came to Global scale in the World Tourism. Also International research experts Conducted tourism problems and effective Marketing approaches in the Business Tourism Industry (Santos, V., Sousa, B., Ramos, P., & Valeri, M. (2022). Emotions and involvement in tourism settings. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25(10), 1526-1531.) additionally, it was studied Green Marketing (Cheng, Y. H., Chang, K. C., Cheng, Y. S., & Hsiao, C. J. (2022). Influences, It is important to mention Turkish researchers on exploring casual relationships among Tourism in CA countries (Azam, M., Ahmad, B., & Ozturk, I. (2021). Especially, research results on the influences of Behavioral Studies are important (Bastiaansen, M., Straatman, S., Mitas, O., Stekelenburg,

J., & Jansen, S. (2022). Research studies on Smart Tourism Design (Fitchett, J., Lindberg, F., & Martin, D. M. (2021) and (Xiang, Z., Stienmetz, J., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2021).) as well as case study approach to sustainability-oriented innovation the works has very interesting facts (Nanni, A., & Ulqinaku, A. (2020). Mortality threats and technology effects on tourism. *Annals of tourism research*.). Morality threats and technological effects on the tourism sphere have good treatments.

Table 1: Number of foreign tourists in Uzbekistan

Years	Number of tourists	Rate change
2014	1.862.000	-5%
2015	1.918.000	3%
2016	2.027.000	6%
2017	2.690.000	33%
2018	5.346.000	99%
2019	6.748.501	26%
2020	1.504.000	-78%
2021	1.881.350	25%

Source: <http://data.worldbank.org>

According to Table 1, The tourism industry in Uzbekistan has shown sustainable development since 2014, for example, 2 million tourists arrived in Uzbekistan in 2016, which is 6 percent more than in 2015, and 26 percent more tourists were received in 2019 than in the previous year. However, after the pandemic, the tourism sector faced a crisis, and tourist flows were significantly reduced. For example, in 2020, 78 percent fewer tourists were received than in 2019. 2021 showed the recovery of the industry in the country, which is evidenced by an increase in the tourist flow by 25 percent more than in the previous year, that is, it amounted to 1,881,350 people.

Data collection, Method and Materials

For study specification as well as Inbound Development Tourism in Uzbekistan, official sources information World Bank Group and State Committee of Republic of Uzbekistan for the development of Tourism, the data report used for 2020-2021.

This study is based on primary and secondary data. The data is being collected from the structured as well as frame questionnaire. The data is collected to make the questionnaire through mailing in Google Forms under the simple random sampling method. In order to ensure about the foreign tourists' expectations and preferences are appropriately represented in the sample self-designed questionnaire has been prepared for collecting the data.

For conducting the survey, a total number of 7 students of TSUOS were selected as interviewers and supervisor as well as a total of 3 employees working in URG Company, Union Relatives Group as general manager of the company.

This self-designed questionnaire was divided into 2 parts demographic question as well as second part mention questions related to variables. To measure the responses of foreign tourists the Likert 5 scale points is used. These questions that were qualitative but also, quotative by making a use of 5 scale point rating with scores:

1. Highly satisfied, 2. Satisfied, 3. Natural, 4. Dissatisfied, 5. Highly dissatisfied.

Objectives of the research study

Table 2 Inbound (arrival)

Year	2019		2020	
From Cis	6260.1	92.7%	1420.3	94.4%
Other countries	488.4	7.25%	83.8	5.5%
Total	97.48.5		15.4.1	

Source: <https://stat.uz/uz/> The State Committee of The Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics

During the period of 2019-2020 in Uzbekistan inbound tourist number achieved to 6260.1 thousand people and this result gives 92.7% of total number of tourists from CIS countries. From other foreign countries total tourists number achieved 488.4 thousand people, the result shows 7.23% from the total number of International Tourists.

The next period 2020 the total number of tourists achieved 1420.3 thousand people from CIS countries and gives 94.4% from total number and other countries inbound tourists consisted of 83.8 thousand people showing 5.5% from total number. The result shows that over a period of 2019-2020 the arrival of International tourist was decreased to 1.7% from CIS countries and decreased to 1.73% from other foreign countries.

Table 3 Outbound (Departure)

Year	2019		2020	
For Cis	7977.7	94.5%	1843.3	92.1%
Other countries	480.1	5.5%	158.2	7.9%
Total	8437.8		2001.5	

Source: <https://stat.uz/uz/> The State Committee of The Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics

According to Table 3, For the period of 2019-2020, the outbound indicator for Uzbek Citizens who travelled to CIS countries were 7977.7 thousand people which shows 94.5% of the total numbers and in 2020 the total number reached to 1843.3 which shows 92.1% from total departures. Whereas travelling tourist numbers to other foreign countries achieved 480.1 thousand people that shows 5.5% in 2019 and the next year the total numbers reached 158.2 thousand people which consisting 7.9% from total number of travellers. The total numbers of flow in citizen decreased from 8437.8 to 2001.5 over a period of 2019-2020. Overall result represents the decreasing percentage outbound tourism reached to 2.4% to CIS countries.

Result and Analysis

The study shows the results that tourist who came to Uzbekistan having certain motivation with sufficient information. Foreign tourists describe the interest to the historical heritage of Uzbekistan as well as museums, picture galleries, short excursions, MICE events, shopping, hospitality extra facilities, transportation, and F/B (Food and Beverage) service. Most of the foreign tourists got satisfied facility standards, service transport, and food of service quality. This study shows the satisfaction of safety during their period of visiting.

This study was conducted among foreign visitors who travelled to Uzbekistan. In survey process a total number of 300 respondents were involved. This research survey was conducted in the territory of Tashkent.

In Uzbekistan Tourism had taken an important play when there was an entry of Republic in 1993 into the UN world Tourism Organisation (UNWTO).

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